

Bayesian non-parametric models in reliability

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Abstract

In this paper we discuss two applications of Bayesian non-parametric modelling to problems in reliability theory.

In the first application we use data from software reliability, in which a piece of software is tested independently by a panel of reviewers. Each reviewer has a different level of skill, and the faults have different levels of detectability. Our goal is to simultaneously cluster the reviewers into groups of similar skill, and faults into groups of similar detectability, and ultimately estimate the number of faults which have not been detected. This setting is equivalent to capture-recapture problems incorporating heterogeneity. One common approach to this problem is to specify a biclustering finite mixture model. In this instance we instead use the Dirichlet Process Prior as the generative model for the detection of each fault by each reviewer, and then *a posteriori* we group the reviewers and faults.

In the second application we consider the non-parametric estimation of bathtub hazard rate functions. A bathtub function consists of a high initial failure rate, equivalent to the high infant mortality rate shared both by animals and manufactured systems, after which the hazard rate decreases to a period of rare failures. Finally the hazard rate increases towards the end of the life of the system. In this case we use the Gamma Process Prior as the basis of a number of different specifications of such bathtub shaped hazard rates.

1. INTRODUCTION

The study of reliability encompasses a number of fields of research. It includes applications of survival analysis to the analysis of times to failure of manufactured items, such as cars or computers. Failures may be system wide, or specific to components or subsystems. Analysis may include the integration of testing, inspection, maintenance and improvement policies and strategies. Warranty Analysis uses the results of such analyses to estimate the financial risk companies run when selling products under warranty, and aids in the pricing of warranties. There are numerous texts which give thorough introductions to the field [1, 2, 3, 4, 5].

Here we consider two specific instances of reliability analysis, using Bayesian nonparametric methods as the key inference tool. In the first application we use methods from capture-recapture to estimate the number of errors in a piece of software after testing by a panel of independent reviewers. In the second application we consider the problem of estimating the instantaneous risk of failure in the setting where the failure rate is high at early ages, reduces during a period of peak performance, and then finally increases towards the end of the feasible life of the system.

This brief paper presents only the basic details of work in progress on these two applications, and some technical details are omitted due to space restrictions.

2. COUNTING ERRORS IN SOFTWARE

Consider the situation in which we have a piece of software and wish to estimate how many errors N it contains. We enrol a panel of m reviewers, and get them to test the software, and identify the errors they discover. After this process is complete we compare the lists of errors they have found, and identify any which have been identified by

multiple reviewers. Given the n distinct errors identified, we lay out a $n \times m$ detection indicator matrix Y as our data. The matrix has entries

$$Y_{ij} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if error } i \text{ was detected by reviewer } j, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Each row in the matrix has at least one non-zero element, and if N were known we would extend the matrix with $N - n$ further rows of all zeroes corresponding to the undetected faults.

This is identical to the marked capture-recapture problem which commonly occurs in ecology: the goal is to estimate the size N of an animal population from m occasions at which samples of animals are captured. The animals are identifiable (they carry or are given ‘marks’ to ensure this), and animals may be captured on more than one occasion.

There is an extensive literature on capture-recapture estimation [6, 7, 8, 9, 10], including earlier treatments of the error detection application that we treat here [11]. The reason that this problem has attracted so much sustained and detailed attention is that estimators of N are subject to significant bias in the presence of heterogeneity: faults differ in their detectability, and reviewers differ in their skill. We take as an example the data from Basu (1988) [12] where $m = 6$ reviewers tested a piece of software and found a total of $n = 43$ distinct faults. The capture matrix Y for this data set is shown (transposed) in Figure 1: the rows correspond to reviewers and the columns to faults. It is easily seen that Reviewers 1 and 4 are particularly skilled (each finding more faults than the other Reviewers), and that fault 17 is particularly easy to find (found by five out of six Reviewers).

Figure 1: Detection of faults in a piece of software reported by Basu (1998) [12]. There are $m = 6$ reviewers (the rows) and $n = 43$ faults detected. Each shaded square represents a detection of a fault by a reviewer.

We start our modelling by assuming that each fault i has different detectability θ_{ij} when it is being sought by Reviewer j , and thus that

$$Y_{ij} \sim \text{Bernoulli}(\theta_{ij}) . \quad (2)$$

A distinct probability θ_{ij} for every fault-reviewer combination clearly over-parameterises the problem, requiring $N \times m$ independent values. There have been a number of approaches to reducing the number of degrees of freedom of the detectability matrix $\Theta = \{\theta_{ij}\}$, introducing a set of parameters ψ of lower dimension which determine the entries of Θ . This leads to the general capture-recapture likelihood

$$L(\psi, N|Y) = \frac{N!}{n!(N-n)!} p_0(\psi)^{N-n} \prod_{i=1}^n \prod_{j=1}^m \theta_{ij}(\psi)^{y_{ij}} (1 - \theta_{ij}(\psi))^{1-y_{ij}} . \quad (3)$$

One such approach to specifying $\Theta(\psi)$ uses a finite mixture, in which each fault belongs to one of $R < n$ latent classes, each class having an a priori probability π_r . We then either treat all reviewers as distinct (thus Θ has $R \times m$ parameters), or alternatively introduce a second finite mixture in which each reviewers belongs to one of $C < m$ latent classes with a priori probabilities κ_c . This further reduces the effective dimension of Θ to $R \times C$ (although we need $R-1$ additional parameters to specify $\{\pi_r\}$ and $C-1$ to specify $\{\kappa_c\}$). This two-way clustering approach is known as biclustering. Pledger (2000) [8] gave a systematic treatment of finite mixture methods in capture-recapture. Estimation, for fixed R and C , is straightforward using the EM algorithm - though convergence can be slow and impeded by multiple local maxima in (3). Trans-dimensional Bayesian approaches can eliminate the need to fit and compare multiple models of distinct mixture dimensions R and C , but instead explore the full range of possible dimensions using a Reversible Jump MCMC sampler [13].

Dirichlet Process Mixtures (DPM) (see e.g. [14]) form an alternative construction for the finite mixture method of analysing capture-recapture data. Such non-parametric approaches have been applied in this setting before (e.g.

[15]), and in particular Manrique-Vallier (2016) [16] has applied a DPM to capture-recapture data. In this paper we extend the treatment of Manrique-Vallier to the case of biclustering in capture-recapture.

2.1 Model specification

The biclustered formulation of the capture-recapture problem is as follows. Firstly we define a Bernoulli model for the entries of the capture-recapture matrix Y where both rows and columns are clustered. We let $k_i \in \{1, \dots, R\}$ be the label of the row cluster containing fault i , and $\ell_j \in \{1, \dots, C\}$ be the label of the column clustering containing fault j . Then, following Meeds and Roweis (2007) [17] (see also [18]),

$$\begin{aligned}
Y_{ij}|k_i = r, \ell_j = c, \Theta &\sim \text{Bernoulli}(\theta_{rc}) \\
k_i|\{\pi\} &\sim \text{Cat}_R(\{\pi\}) \\
\pi_r(\mathbf{v}) &= v_r \prod_{k < r} (1 - v_k) \\
v_r|\alpha &\sim \text{Beta}(1, \alpha) \\
\ell_j|\kappa &\sim \text{Cat}_C(\kappa) \\
\kappa_c(\mathbf{w}) &= w_c \prod_{k < c} (1 - w_k) \\
w_c|\beta &\sim \text{Beta}(1, \beta) \\
\theta_{rc} &\sim G_0(\psi) \quad r, c = 1, \dots, \infty
\end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

The detection probabilities θ_{rc} in the latent class rc (row group r and column group c) are drawn from a base measure $G_0(\psi)$. A logical choice for this distribution is a Beta distribution, with parameters $\psi = (a, b)$ being chosen to reflect the likely range of capture probabilities.

The specification in (4) uses the stick-breaking algorithm of Sethuraman [19] to generate the two sets of a priori membership probabilities $\{\pi_r\}_{r=1}^{\infty}$ for the row classes and $\{\kappa_c\}_{c=1}^{\infty}$ for the column classes. In principle these sets of probabilities have infinite dimension, but in practice we truncate these sets at finite dimensions R^* and C^* due to the probabilities being stochastically decreasing in r and c respectively. In general only a very small number ($R \ll R^*$ and $C \ll C^*$) of these prior probabilities are nonzero, and these correspond to the similarly small sets of latent classes in the regular finite mixture case.

In order to allow the unknown population size N in the capture-recapture setting we extend the model with

$$\begin{aligned}
N|\eta &\sim \text{Geometric}(1 - \eta) \\
\mathbf{f}_0|N, \Theta, \mathbf{v}, \ell &\sim \text{Multinomial}(N - n, \mathbf{p}_0(\theta, \mathbf{v}, \ell)) \\
p_{0r}(\Theta, \mathbf{v}, \ell) &\propto w_r(\mathbf{v}) \prod_{c=1}^{C^*} (1 - \theta_{rc})^{\sum_j I(\ell_j=c)} \quad \text{with } \sum_r p_{0r} = 1
\end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

where $p_{0r}(\Theta)$ is the probability that a fault from row class r will go undetected, and \mathbf{f}_0 is the vector of counts of undetected faults in each of the classes. To complete the model suitable priors are required for the stick-breaking parameters α and β , and for the parameter ψ of the base measure G_0 .

With the above construction we can construct an MCMC sampler which explores latent class models of varying dimension automatically. With simple choices of priors and the base measure all of the sampler steps are Gibbs updates, and the sampler mixes rapidly.

2.2 Application

When applied to the data in Figure 1 we obtain the posterior distribution for the number of undetected faults $N - n$ shown in Figure 2. The posterior mean is 77, the posterior median is 44, and the wide 95% credible interval is (13,288) indicates a high degree of uncertainty about the number of faults remaining unseen. Figure 3 shows the posterior predictive distribution of detection of faults by reviewers, corresponding to the data in Figure 1. The diagram confirms the skill of Reviewers 1 and 4, and the ease of detection of fault 17.

A determination of the number of clusters in a DPM can be made by identifying the proportion of times rows or columns have the same component labels over the set of MCMC samples. Taking this co-clustering approach we

find that the reviewers divide into two clusters (Reviewers 1 and 4 vs. the rest). The faults divide into four clusters with Fault 17 in a cluster on its own, and three further groups of faults with similar detectability patterns across the six reviewers.

Figure 2: Posterior distribution of the number of undetected faults.

Figure 3: Posterior predictive distribution $P(Y_{ij} = 1|Y)$ for faults reported in Basu (1998) [12]. The intensity of colour represents the likelihood of detection.

3. ESTIMATING BATHTUB HAZARD RATE FUNCTIONS

In survival analysis, our interest is in the distribution of the time to failure of members of a population. For example, Figure 4 shows the distribution of lengths of life for cohorts in Denmark born in 1835 and 1933 [20]. These show distributions with high infant mortality, followed by a low, though nonzero, risk of death through late childhood to middle age, and then a constantly increasing death rate in late adulthood. The distributions show the dramatically improved life expectancies for the 1933 cohort compared to 1835, driven predominantly by the near elimination of infant and childhood mortality.

These data can be transformed into the survival function, the proportion of individuals who survive at least time t : $\bar{F}(t) = \Pr(T > t)$, and the hazard rate function

$$\lambda(t) = -\frac{d \log \bar{F}(t)}{dt} \tag{6}$$

which quantifies the instantaneous rate of failure at time t . These functions are displayed in Figure 5 for the 1835 Danish birth cohort. The hazard rate function $\lambda(t)$ in Figure 5(b) shows the typical ‘bathtub’ shape: a high initial failure rate, a period of sustained low rate, and a final increasing rate. It is the non-parametric modelling of bathtub hazard rate functions that is the focus of this section.

Although many parametric models for bathtub hazard rate functions exist (e.g. [21]), they lack the flexibility to accommodate a wide range of situations, such as the case where the middle age low rate period may be particularly

Figure 4: Distribution of ages at death for the (a) 1835 and (b) 1933 Danish birth cohorts. (From the Human Mortality Database, www.mortality.org, [20])

Figure 5: (a) Survival function $\bar{F}(t) = 1 - F(t)$ and (b) hazard rate function $\lambda(t)$ for the 1835 Danish birth cohorts (From the Human Mortality Database, www.mortality.org, [20])

long. The long standing non-parametric Kaplan-Meier estimator [22] does have full flexibility in this respect, but is not constrained in any way, and we thus cannot impose the bathtub shape requirement on it. Instead, we extend the approach of Lo and Weng (1989) [23] who used a Gamma Process Prior to specify hazard rate functions of various forms. In their general approach the hazard rate function is specified through the partial integral of a non-negative function G which is drawn from a Gamma Process Prior:

$$\lambda(t) = \lambda_0 + \int_0^\infty \kappa(u|t) G(du) \quad (7)$$

Differing behaviours (e.g. non-increasing or non-decreasing) can be imposed through the choice of the kernel function $\kappa(u|t)$. They proposed the bathtub function symmetric about a cut point a using the kernel function

$$\kappa_{\text{LWB}}(u|t) = I(0 < u \leq |t - a|), \quad \text{with } a > 0 \quad (8)$$

This form was later generalised by Ho (2011) [24] with the more flexible form

$$\kappa_{\text{HBT}}(u|t) = I(t \leq u < a) + I(a < u \leq t) \quad \text{with } a > 0 \quad (9)$$

For reasons explained below, these specifications all lead to hazard rate functions that are staircases, i.e. piecewise constant, when G is drawn from a Gamma Process prior. This ‘jumpy’ behaviour is avoided by the kernel proposed by Jankowski and Wellner (2009) [25]

$$\kappa_{\text{HCV}}(u|t) = I(t \leq u < a)(u - t) + I(a < u \leq t)(t - u) \quad \text{with } a > 0 \quad (10)$$

which leads to a piecewise linear hazard rate. Likelihood based inference for this specification has been carried out by Fani et al. (2021) [26]. We also propose the construction based on the requirement that the gradient of $\log \lambda(t)$ be non-decreasing

$$\begin{aligned} \log \lambda(t) &= \log \lambda_0 + w_0 t + \int_0^\infty \kappa_{\text{IFR}}(u|t) G(du) \\ \kappa_{\text{IFR}}(u|t) &= I(u < t) \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

Here $\lambda(t)$ is non-decreasing if $w_0 \geq 0$, but $w_0 < 0$ leads to a bathtub shape. The non-decreasing constraint is applied to the gradient of $\log \lambda(t)$ in order that $\lambda(t)$ always be non-negative. We now consider a fully Bayesian treatment of these various specifications where $G(\cdot)$ is drawn from a Gamma Process Prior.

3.1 Gamma Process Prior

In the hazard rate specifications above G is a draw from a Gamma Process prior $G \sim \text{GaPP}(\alpha G_0, \beta)$ with shape parameter $\alpha > 0$, rate parameter $\beta > 0$ and base probability measure $G_0(\cdot)$ defined on the space \mathbb{R}^+ . A draw from the Gamma Process Prior can be formed by drawing first from a Dirichlet Process Prior $\text{DPP}(\alpha G_0)$ and then scaling the resulting weights by an independent Gamma random variable drawn from $\gamma \sim \text{Gamma}(\alpha, \beta)$. To form the draw from the Dirichlet Process Prior we again use stick-breaking construction of Sethuraman (1994) [19]. We note that an alternative stick-breaking construction for the Gamma Process prior was developed by Roychowdhury and Kulis [27, 28].

In the gamma-scaled Dirichlet Process Prior method, a draw from the prior $\text{GaPP}(\alpha G_0, \beta)$ is

$$G(du) = \gamma \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} v_k \prod_{\ell < k} (1 - v_\ell) \delta_{\theta_k}(du) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} w_k(\gamma, \mathbf{v}) \delta_{\theta_k}(du) \quad (12)$$

where $\gamma \sim \text{Ga}(\alpha, \beta)$, $v_k \stackrel{\text{iid}}{\sim} \text{Beta}(1, \alpha)$, and $\theta_k \stackrel{\text{iid}}{\sim} G_0$ for $k = 1, 2, \dots$. A draw from this prior is discrete: there is a countably infinite set of locations $\{\theta_k\}_{k=1}^{\infty}$ and each is associated with a weight $\{w_k\}_{k=1}^{\infty}$. These weights are the product of the Gamma random draw γ and the usual Dirichlet Process Prior (DPP) weights $\{\tilde{w}_k\}_{k=1}^{\infty}$. These unscaled DPP weights add to 1, the scaled weights w_k sum up to the total mass γ , and so we have

$$w_k(\gamma, \mathbf{v}) = \gamma \tilde{w}_k(\mathbf{v}) = \gamma v_k \prod_{\ell < k} (1 - v_\ell) \quad (13)$$

for $k = 1, 2, \dots$. The weights w_k are stochastically decreasing in k which means that if we truncate the sum in (12) at some sufficiently large finite K then the finite sum of the weights $\sum_{k=1}^K w_k$ will be very close to γ . In practice we draw K locations θ_k , and construct the first $K - 1$ weights using (13). The weight of the last location is assigned to be $w_K = \gamma - \sum_{k=1}^{K-1} w_k$ so that the weights exactly add to γ . If K is sufficiently large then the effect of this approximation is negligible.

Figure 6(a) shows an example set of weights and locations in a random draw from a Gamma Process Prior $G \sim \text{GaPP}(\alpha G_0, \beta)$. As is typical for models of this kind there are a small number of large weights, and a large number of weights that are for practical purposes negligible. Figure 6(b) shows the hazard rate function according to the specification in (9). The kernel leads to a staircase hazard rate, with a change from decreasing to increasing behaviour at the cutpoint a , indicated by the vertical dashed line. The kernel (10) transforms the staircase function into a piecewise linear function, shown in Figure 7(a) using the same draw. The equivalent log convex hazard rate function is shown in Figure 7(b).

Figure 6: (a) Draw of locations and weights $\{(\theta_k, w_k)\}_{k=1}^K$ from a Gamma Process Prior. (b) Staircase hazard rate function from (9) using these locations and weights.

Figure 7: (a) Piecewise linear hazard rate from (10) and (b) Log convex hazard rate function from (11) using the locations and weights from Figure 6(a).

A fully hierarchical Bayesian model for G can be completed by choosing a form for G_0 , with parameters ψ , and specifying suitable priors for α , β , γ , ν and ϕ . For example if $G_0(\psi) = \text{Exp}(\nu, \psi)$ then we can set

$$\begin{aligned}
 \lambda_0 &\sim \text{Ga}(s_1, s_2) \\
 a &\sim \text{Ga}(c_1, c_2) \\
 \alpha &\sim \text{Ga}(a_1, a_2) \\
 \beta &\sim \text{Ga}(b_1, b_2) \\
 \nu &\sim \text{Ga}(g_1, g_2) \\
 \phi &\sim \text{Ga}(f_1, f_2)
 \end{aligned} \tag{14}$$

for specified non-negative constants $\{s_1, s_2, c_1, c_2, a_1, a_2, b_1, b_2, g_1, g_2, f_1, f_2\}$. MCMC samplers can be straightforwardly constructed, although almost all steps are Metropolis-Hastings steps, needing care in constructing well tuned samplers.

3.2 Example

To demonstrate the model we have described above we have taken a failure time data set from Kumar et al. (1989) [29] on failure times of Load Haul Dump machines. We have taken the data from one machine (A), and delayed the failure times in the later half of the data by a fixed amount to create a data set with a clear bathtub failure distribution. The failure times are shown in Figure 8.

100 draws from the Bayesian non-parametric posterior are shown in Figure 9, where a good fit is achieved. In particular the fitted model correctly reproduces the long interval of zero failures with a low fitted failure rate $\lambda(t)$. For comparison we have also fitted a typical parametric model known as the Modified Exponentiated Weibull (MEW) [21]. This four parameter model $(\alpha, \beta, \mu, \nu)$ has hazard rate

$$\lambda(t) = \mu\beta (\mu t)^{\beta-1} e^{(\mu t)^\beta} \left[\nu + \alpha \left(e^{(\mu t)^\beta} - 1 \right)^{\alpha-1} \right] \tag{15}$$

The results are shown in Figure 10, and it is clear that the parametric model is not able to reproduce the data quite as well in the low failure rate interval. A numerical measure of the relative goodness of fit of the two models is provided by the WAIC (analogous to the AIC, see [30, 31]) with a smaller WAIC indicating a better fit. The MEW fit has a WAIC value of 91.2, compared to the more favourable 83.5 value for the non-parametric fit.

Figure 8: Failure times, modified from [29].

Figure 9: Bayesian non-parametric piecewise linear hazard rate fit to the data in Figure 8: (a) posterior probability density and (b) estimated hazard rate function $\lambda(t)$ (posterior median shown in red, with 100 samples);

4. CONCLUDING REMARKS

In this short paper we have applied Bayesian non-parametric methods to two well known settings in reliability theory. We have found in both cases that this approach is conceptually simple and able to cope with data with a wide range of behaviours.

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Figure 10: Four parameter parametric fit to the data in Figure 8 using the model of Al Essa et al. (2023) [21]: (a) posterior probability density and (b) estimated hazard rate function $\lambda(t)$ (posterior median shown in red, with 100 samples);

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